

Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling: Wind energy applications

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1 Introduction

Modern wind turbines rotor span elevations from 30 to 250 m above the surface. Depending on the atmospheric stability conditions, this corresponds either to a relatively shallow area of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) in convective conditions, or the entire ABL and above it for strongly stable conditions. Beside mean wind speeds and directions, turbulence induced by the terrain heavily impacts loads and power performance. In this chapter, a number of applications are described, all aiming at increasing the value of ABL measurements for Wind Energy (WE) purposes.

The value of ABL remote sensing technologies for WE purposes has been assessed from the beginning of modern WE in the late 1970s, see (Hooke, 1981). The primary focus has been and remains the measurement of wind speed and direction, for example using sodar technology, but recently most of all using Doppler Lidars (DL) which have been extensively utilised for WE since the late 2000s, due to technical advances in fibre optics (Peña et al., 2015). Secondary uses of ABL remote sensing are temperature- and humidity profiling, for research purposes so far.

The primary focus on wind speed and direction is easily explained by the very high sensitivity of wind turbine power production and mechanical loads to the wind field. Such sensitivities are clearly expressed in industry guidelines such as (DNV, 2011). The long-term energy yield of a wind turbine is sensitive to small changes in the wind speed distribution, and in particular the mean wind speed where a few percent changes lead to large deviations between pre-construction estimates and actual production (Todd et al. 2022). Equally important are fatigue (normal operation, mainly turbulence-driven) and extreme (storm) loads induced by the wind. Therefore, a fine characterization of wind conditions is an essential part of project planning, both for commercial and regulatory (safety, insurance) purposes. Such activities are today covered by industry standards within the IEC61400 series in particular:

- -1 and -3 that are design standards,
- -15 for site suitability
- -12 for power performance (including the use of doppler lidars)
- -50 for wind measurement technologies.

The latter suite of standards (IEC61400-50) is particularly relevant for PROBE, it covers:

- IEC61400-50-1: met masts, nacelle- and spinner instruments
- IEC61400-50-2: ground-based lidars (excluding scanning lidars)
- IEC61400-50-3: nacelle lidars

- IEC61400-50-4: floating lidar systems.
- IEC61400-50-5: scanning lidars

The four last documents deal with technologies which cover the main uses of remote sensing instruments in WE today, as illustrated below (and discussed in more detail in the next section). The IEC standards are supplemented with industry guidelines such as DNVs:

- “Guidelines on dual scanning lidar measurements for wind resource assessments” (2024)
- “DNV-RP-0661 Lidar-measured turbulence intensity for wind turbines” (2023)

Technology	Use case and added value	Illustration
Ground-based lidars	Short-term (1-3 years) measurement of wind speed and wind direction, prior to construction. These data are then long-term corrected and spatially extrapolated to each planned turbine position and used for estimating future energy production. Cost: ~€150k.	
Nacelle lidars	Short term (<1 year) measurement of the incoming wind speed at hub height and/or across an existing wind turbine rotor. These data are used for assessing how much a given turbine produces at a given wind speed. These results are then compared with commercially binding contractual agreements undertaken by the project owner and the wind turbine manufacturer prior to the construction of the wind farm. Cost: €80k.	

<p>Floating lidar systems</p>	<p>Same as for ground-based lidars, but for offshore projects where these instruments replace costly met towers. Cost: €1m/year.</p>	
<p>Scanning lidars</p>	<p>Scanning lidars are typically used, for commercial projects, for the same purposes as floating lidar systems: scanning lidars are deployed at the coastline and measure wind conditions up to approx. 10 to 20 km maximum. Cost: €300-500k.</p> <p>For research purposes scanning lidars, often used in dual- or triple lidar configurations, are used for characterising finely complex wind fields (due for instance to orography).</p>	

Examples of recent, state of the art wind energy ABL measurement campaigns are provided below:

- [Perdigao](#) (complex terrain)
- [Alaiz](#) (complex terrain)
- [Awaken](#) (onshore flat terrain)
- [WFIP-3](#) (offshore)

Furthermore, an almost exhaustive overview of publicly available wind datasets is maintained on the Wind Resource Assessment Group wiki page: <https://groups.io/g/wrag/wiki/13236>.

2 Low-level jet detection

The nocturnal Low-Level Jet (LLJ) is a very common atmospheric phenomenon with clear implications for wind resource assessment (Weide-Luiz and Fiedler, 2022). In the framework of the PANAME initiative in the Paris region, continuous measurements of wind speed and vertical velocity profiles were recorded with two Doppler Wind Lidars (DWL) - for the first time allowing for a detailed investigation of the summertime LLJ characteristics in the region (Cespedes et al., 2024). Jets are detected for 70% of the examined nights, often simultaneously at an urban (QUALAIR-SU) and a suburban site (SIRTA) highlighting the LLJ regional spatial extent. Emerging at around sunset, the mean LLJ duration is ~10 h, the mean wind speed is ~9 m/s, and the average core height is 400 m above the city. For many jets, results show signatures in the temporal evolution that indicate that the inertial oscillation mechanism plays a role in the jet development: a clockwise veering of the wind direction

and a rapid acceleration followed by a slower deceleration. The LLJ core wind shear induces variance in the vertical velocity above the urban canopy layer (Fig. 2.1) with ramifications for the wind power production.

Figure 2.1: Mean profiles of a) horizontal wind speed and b) median profiles of vertical velocity variance σ_w^2 . The solid lines represent the composite profile with all 30-min profiles detected as LLJ, and the shadows denote $1\pm\text{std}$. Each panel presents the respective profiles for each σ_w^2 class: red is low σ_w^2 , orange is moderate and blue is strong σ_w^2 . Cespedes et al (2024)

3 Offshore atmospheric stability

Upon request from the Carbon Trust Offshore Wind Accelerator (OWA), a UK-based offshore wind R&D initiative, the Radiometry and Atmospheric Profiling (RAP) project¹ was carried out by a consortium formed by C2Wind, the Institute of Methodologies for the Environmental Analysis of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IMAA), and the Hans-Ertel-Centre for Weather Research (HErZ) at the University of Cologne. The project aimed at:

- Gaining an understanding of the suitability of mesoscale NWP modelled temperature profiles for use within offshore energy yield assessment, considering the impact of atmospheric stability on turbine wakes and interaction loss predictions.
- Understanding the best technologies available for measuring atmospheric profiles, specifically investigating microwave profile radiometers.
- Designing a detailed measurement campaign to test and validate microwave profile radiometers, and gain confidence in atmospheric stability statistics provided by mesoscale NWP models.
- Investigating opportunities for future research and provide recommendations for further work.

The work consisted of four Work Packages (WP1):

- WP1 focused on providing tools and methods for deriving atmospheric stability metrics from measurement (excluding radiometers) and model data, as well as comparisons between both.
- WP2 provided detailed explanations on microwave radiometer (MWR) technology, with references to the literature and recent offshore measurement campaigns.
- WP3 discussed the added value of MWR for offshore wind purposes.

¹ See <https://www.carbontrust.com/news-and-insights/tenders/offshore-wind-accelerator-radiometry-and-atmospheric-profiling-scoping-study>

- WP4 concluded the study with recommendation for an onshore and offshore MWR test campaigns.

Overall, the project concluded that:

- At an offshore wind site, atmospheric stability near the surface can be derived from surface measurements or model data; yet, near- and above hub height (i.e. between 100 and 300m, above any practically feasible offshore met mast height), the atmospheric stability conditions may sometimes differ from the surface conditions.
- Model data may help guess what these atmospheric stability conditions are, but the uncertainty in these model data can be detrimental to the validation of wake models, in particular for long-range wake effects;
- MWR has proven, onshore but also offshore, to be a trusted source of temperature measurements across the boundary layer for the meteorological community;
- The RAP project has identified that the MWR could provide similar benefits for offshore wind measurement, provided that at least one dedicated measurement test campaign for wind energy applications is carried out.

Project results were presented at the EGU 2022² and a journal paper will be submitted.

4 Short-term forecasts of low-level wind

An important question for wind energy applications is **how many ground-based Doppler wind lidars, one of the core ABL network-capable instruments within PROBE, are necessary to improve the short-term forecasts of low-level winds over a specific target domain**. Here, the Ensemble Sensitivity Analysis (ESA) approach is used (Griewank et al., 2023). The ESA method allows us to estimate the potential of the instruments before the observational network is built since this approach does not require real observations. The ESA approach was applied to a convective-scale 1000-member ensemble over Germany (Necker et al., 2020), which was obtained from the full-physics non-hydrostatic regional SCALE-RM model with horizontal resolution 3 km. Within this study the changes in the forecasted wind variance (uncertainty) assuming a hypothetical Doppler wind lidar network consisting of a different number of instruments observations is investigated.

Our study investigates the variance (uncertainty) reduction for the domain-averaged low-level wind speed at 80 m which is a typical hub-height of wind turbines. The forecasted low-level wind speed was averaged within the Rhein-Ruhr area (RRA, shown by gray rectangle in Fig. 4.1). The locations of the surface stations operationally used for assimilation by DWD are shown as well as the hypothetical wind lidar observations. For this analysis, we also accounted for a localization scale of the assimilation system to calculate the explicit sensitivity using the inverse of the background covariance B-matrix (Nomokonova et al., 2022).

² <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/EGU22-12954.html>

Figure 4.1: Distribution of the stations used for variance (uncertainty) reduction calculations. The blue dots correspond to the surface stations. The green dots indicate location of hypothetical wind lidar observations. Magenta dots denote the model the model grid used for the state vector. Figure adapted from Nomokonova et al., (2022)

In our analysis the impact of a network of Doppler lidars was evaluated relative to the impact of surface observations. First, we estimated the variance reduction in the forecast metrics achieved from the surface stations located in and surrounding RRA (Fig. 4.1). At the next step, we calculated the variance reduction using the simulated data for the surface stations and a network of Doppler lidars. Locations of the hypothetical Doppler lidars were randomly chosen from the locations of surface stations. We calculated the relative change in the variance reduction $\Delta\sigma_r^2$ as the evaluation metric which is the variance of a forecasted metric resulting from incorporation of data from surface stations and Doppler lidars relative to the original variance of the forecasted metric. The experiments were performed for different combinations of the number of Doppler lidars in the network, the number of available range layers (from 80 m to 2.8 km) included in the Doppler lidar wind profiles, and the forecast lead time.

Figure 4.2: Relative change in variance $\Delta\sigma_r^2$ for different numbers of wind lidars in the network. The forecast metric is the u (a) and v -component (b) of the 80 m wind. Wind lidars observations are available at 1 (blue line), 3 (orange line), and 5 (green line) levels. The solid lines show the mean values over the 50 random locations sets of the wind lidars. The shadow areas denote 25th and 75th percentiles. Figure adopted from Nomokonova et al., (2022)

Figure 4.2 summarises the changes in the variance reduction of the 3-hour forecast of horizontal wind components. Both wind components indicate a weak saturation effect and show divergence from the linear dependence starting at 20-30 wind lidars in the network for at least 3 levels in the wind profiles. Less pronounced saturation effect can be found for the case when only one level is available in the wind lidar profile. The analysed cases indicate that on average 25 Doppler lidars give 3 times better $\Delta\sigma_r^2$ than surface stations only included in the network.

Figure 4.3 summarises the impact of assimilation of surface stations and 25 Doppler lidars on the relative change in the variance reduction $\Delta\sigma_r^2$ with respect to the assimilation of surface stations only. The results show that the

impact of a Doppler lidar network strongly depends on the available range levels in the wind profiles. The available range levels can be limited e.g. by optically thick clouds, fog, and hydrometeors. When only one layer (up to 80 m) is available in the wind lidar profile, the expected improvement of $\Delta\sigma^2$ is only a factor of 1.6–2 relative to the effect of surface stations only. Wind profiles available up to 1 km can lead to the expected improvements in $\Delta\sigma^2$ by a factor of 2.3–3.3. In contrast to the contribution of lowest altitudes, the contribution from wind observations above 1 km does not lead to considerable improvements.

Figure 4.3: Relative change in variance $\Delta\sigma^2$ averaged over 16 available cases for different lead times. The forecast metric is the u (a) and v -component (b) of the 80 m wind. Calculations were performed for 95 surface stations only (dashed black lines), and for 25 wind lidars in addition to the 95 surface stations (other lines). Wind lidar observations are available at 1 (green lines), 2 (orange lines), 3 (blue lines), 4 (red dotted lines) and 5 (solid black lines) levels. Figure adapted from Nomokonova et al., (2022)

The results show that a wind lidar network composed of 25 instruments bears high potential to significantly improve the low-level wind forecasts and that this impact is influenced by the ABL conditions (e.g. ABL height or cloud base height). More on this study is published in Nomokonova et al. (2022). In principle, the ESA methodology can be applied to arbitrary hypothetical observations relevant to renewable energy (or other) applications.

5 References

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